

***Ketellaeria*: A Taxonomically Less Defined Genus**

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ABSTRACT

Gymnosperm are the plants of the always of the great economic and the evolutionary values. They have the abundant empire in the Mesozoic era; the conservation of the nucleic acid is the significant step in the tracing the evolution of the plants in the geological history of these magnificent plants. The cycadales are considered as the living fossils, only 11 genera of the cycadales have been reported from all over the world. The whole group is represented by the genera of the conifers which are well distributed in the in India and the other part of the world. They are utilised for the fulfilment of the many kinds of the needs of the human beings. In this review article we are working on some of the aspects of the one of the conifer genus entitled as the Ketelaleria. This is the genus which has a very narrow distribution in the current era, however the Long history of the plants can be seen in the late Triassic era. The genus is well distributed in the china and the Vietnam. In India however, few members can be seen but as far as the endemism is concerned these plants are well distributed in the central china. conservation of the plants is necessary for the saving of the belt in the world since the plants is important from economically and the evolutionary point of view.

INTRODUCTION

Gymnosperm has the long evolutionary history, conferales are the sole representatives of the gymnosperms' in cenozoic era. All coniferales are long and they have the needles like leaves, prominent secondary growth can be seen the reproduction occur with the help of the cones, the cones are the males and the female, they are presented separately on the different plants. Monoecious and the dioeciously condition of the cones can be found in all the genera's of the coniferales ^[1] (**Figure 1**).

LITERATURE REVIEW

In this genus we are working on the one of the coniferales entitled as the ketellaria. It is the typical genus of the conifers. It possesses the whole of the characters of the conifers. The genus is named after the English nurseryman Ketellaria (1813-1903). The plants are highly distributed in the china and the some of the provinces of the Vietnam ^[2-4] (**Figure 2**).

The tree is about the 40-50 meters in height, plant leaves are of the needles and they have the length of the 4-5 cm and the width of the 3-4 cm. The cones are erect and they are found in the form of the umbel. The anatomy of the plant is typical gymnosperms ^[5]. One can see the all kinds of the pattern of the typical gymnosperms growth pattern (**Figure 3**).

The coppice formation is the common feature in the members of the *Ketellaria*. Whole of the genus of the *Ketellaeria* has the three species in common. These species of the ketellaria are enlisted as. *Ketellaria devidiana*, *Ketellaria evelyniana*, *Ketellaria fortunasi* (**Figure 4**).

Form the evolution point of view the genus is in between the *Pseudolarix* and the *Nothosuga*. The characters are intermediate between the *Pseudolarix* and the *Nothosuga*. However now they are the evolutionary relicts.

Figure 1. *Ketellaria* with cones (sources gymnosperm databases).

Figure 2. *Ketellaalria* in habitat (sources gymnosperm databases).

Figure 3. Branches of the *Ketellaria* gymnosperm with cones (sources IUCN plant list).

Figure 4. Emerging cones of the ketellaria (sources gymnosperm databases).

DISCUSSION

The plants are used highly from the economic and the evolutionary point of view. The wood is used for the formation of the many kinds of the contraction work and the other articles [6]. The seeds are also very useful and they have the reserves of the many kinds of them, metabolites of the medicinal values, the resin and the bark of the plants are utilized for the treatment of the many kinds of the diseases [7-10] (**Table 1**).

Table 1. The major feature of the variations of the three species of the *Ketelallaria* are as follows.

S. No.	<i>K. devidiana</i>	<i>K. evelysnana</i>	<i>K. fortunai</i>
Distribution	The plant is distributed in the China, Veitnam, some of the provenances so of the Guanghi, Guiazhou, Hubei, some of the panes in the Vietnam.	Native place of the plant is the Vietnam and the China. Some of the places of the Yunnan, some plant on the hills of the mountain.	Native place is the Korea and the China and the Guang provinces.
Pattern of the distribution	The tree is distributed to the hills and the mountains	The tree grows at the height of the 500 meters of the mountains	The tree is on the hills as well as on the plains.
Habit and then mature of the plants	The height of the tree is about the 40-50 meters, long, conical in shape, evergreen in nature.	The height of the tree is about the 50-56- meters, the plant is conical in shape. evergreen tree.	The tree is about the 40-45 meters, evergreen in nature.

CONCLUSION

Threat, well the places or the habitat where these plants grows are at the edge of the deterioration. The habitat is degrading due to the over construction of the road and the other constrictions of the human needs. Well this genus is highly endemic and restricted to the China and some places of the Vietnam. The genus is needed to be conserved so that the sources of the metabolites and the other human benefications can be secured. Overall this article touches the some of the aspects of the *Keteleria* genus and their conservation status [11,12].

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